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CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY OF WINTER WHEAT IN THE GANJA-KAZAKH REGION**Guliyeva R.K.,****Huseynzade E.V.***Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
Ganja city, Atatürk Ave. 450***Abstract**

Winter wheat is demanding against predecessor plants. The main requirement for the predecessors is that the field is cleared of plants in time for cultivation and sowing, it is possible to clean the field from weeds, it is possible to collect and preserve moisture and, on the basis of this, to ensure the same level of output, the plants develop well in autumn. Doing it will make it possible to have a good wintering and get a high yield. Black herring is the best predecessor for winter wheat in arid, dry regions. On irrigated and moisture-provided soils, winter wheat is planted with potatoes, annual cereals, corn for green fodder, alfalfa, rapeseed, sorghum, etc. they are good predecessors. The main requirement for the predecessors is that at least 30-45 days before the sowing of autumn crops, the field is free and can be fertilized and plowed. [2, pp194-195]

Keywords: winter wheat, cultivation technology

Should be applied according to the biological characteristics of each variety and the soil-climatic conditions of the region where it is cultivated. Cultivation of the soil should be zonal in nature, should protect the soil from erosion, should be aimed at collecting and preserving moisture. Cultivation of the land with the method of kefiy fiyyat affects the moisture of the planting layer, littering with weeds, which shows the effect of obtaining good outputs and increasing productivity. In the vegetable garden, spring and autumn annual legumes, corn, potatoes, beets, tobacco, cotton, etc. can be cultivated. High agrotechnical care of each plant cultivated in such a field, their harvest should be done quickly, and the field should be plowed and prepared for sowing approximately 35-40 days before winter wheat sowing. In many farms, wheat is sown again instead of winter wheat or barley. In this case, it is necessary to pay more attention to the preparation of the field for sowing. If there is enough moisture in the soil at the time of harvesting the predecessor plant and the field is free of weeds, when harvesting the crop, it is necessary to plow 28-30 cm in the field behind the combine, and immediately trowel and smooth it. After that, it is necessary to carry out cultivation and harrowing to destroy the weeds formed in the field before sowing. Before plowing, 10-15 tons of semi-rotted manure and 1.5-2 centners of superphosphate should be given per hectare. If there are a lot of weed sprouts in the field and the soil is dry, it is recommended to cover the corner with LDQ-10 and LDQ-15 brand disc or slatted cultivators immediately behind the combine harvester at a depth of 5-7 cm, as soon as wheat or barley, which is the predecessor plant, is harvested. If there is a lot of littering with root-loving weeds in the field, it is important to carry out mulching at a depth of 10-12 cm with PPL-5-25, PPL-10-25 plum mulchers. In order to create good conditions for the germination of weeds and ensure quality plowing, it is very important to apply water (deceptive irrigation) at the rate of 500-600 m³ per hectare after covering. 3-4 weeks after seeding, when weeds germinate, plowing is carried out at a depth of 25-30

cm with PLN-6-35, PTK-9-35 brand plows. In the spring, in order to prevent the loss of moisture in the herik field, plowing is carried out with the BZTS-1.0 brand aggregate, then during the whole summer, cultivation is carried out with the KŞP-8, KPS-4 brand aggregates up to 3-5 times as weeds form. The first cultivation is carried out at a depth of 10-12 cm, each subsequent one is shallower than the other, and the cultivation before the last sowing is carried out at a depth of 5-6 cm. This type of cultivation ensures that moisture is retained in the soil and the field remains free of weeds. RVK-3,6, RVK-5,4, VIP-5, combined aggregates are used for better cultivation before sowing. In one run of the unit, the soil is softened, the clods are crushed, the soil is tamped and the microrelief is smoothed. For better soil compaction, harrowing gives good results, it is efficient to use APK-2.5, APK-5.0 combined (ring-shaped harrow and trowel, cotton, tractor) plowing units on soils with sufficient moisture. After the harvest of the predecessors, there is usually little time (time) left until the sowing of autumn crops, so it is necessary to carefully choose the soil cultivation system for autumn crops. If it is more than a month before sowing after the harvest of the predecessor plant, then the field is immediately covered and soon plowed with mulching, or plowed without covering. If there is less than a month left after the harvest of the predecessor plant, then in dry air and weed-free fields, the surface cultivation of the soil is applied at a depth of 10-12 cm, and harrowing is applied. The field is weedy, when the soil is dry, the ridge is covered with a disc trowel to a depth of 5-6 cm. Then the field is irrigated at the rate of 500-600 m³/ha. After the seeds of grain and weeds have germinated, re-covering is done and the plow is lifted. Cultivation and trowel are applied to the field if necessary until sowing. The field is plowed, sowing is carried out immediately after pre-sowing cultivation. After sowing, furrow irrigation is carried out in non-ploughed areas.

Application of fertilizers is one of the important agrotechnical measures that ensure abundant and high-quality harvest. Fertilization system should ensure:

planned high-quality grain harvest; increasing soil fertility; environmental protection; purchase of biologically pure products; high efficiency of fertilizers. Fertilization system should be adjusted so that the balance of nutrients in the soil is positive, regardless of the predecessor plant. Winter wheat takes 25-35 kg of nitrogen, 19-30 kg of phosphorus and 13-20 kg of potassium elements from the soil with each ton of main and additional products. In order to ensure the high efficiency of mineral fertilizers, it is necessary to carry out liming so that the reaction of the soil product is close to neutral (pH-7.0) in fields with acidic soil. Fertilization system for winter wheat consists of putting the soil under the main plow during the main cultivation: under cultivation before sowing ; in rows, or in rows-with sowing during sowing; in the form of feeding during the vegetation period of the plant. Under winter wheat, manure, peat, compost, phosphorus and potassium fertilizers are used as the main fertilizers. Manure is the most valuable fertilizer for all regions where winter wheat is grown . If winter wheat is placed after clean heather, organic fertilizer is given under the plow in autumn, and in black heather, it is applied to the plant occupying the field or directly under winter wheat. When applying organic fertilizer, it should be taken into account that 1 ton of cattle manure contains N-0.5 kg, P₂O₅-2.5 kg, K₂O-0.6 kg (the first year, respectively, 20-30 , 25-36 and 50-60% are used).

Phosphorus and potassium fertilizers are applied under the main plow. A part of the phosphorus fertilizer in the form of granulated superphosphate (15-25 kg P₂O₅ per hectare) is given to the rows with a grain spreading layer. If phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were not given during the main cultivation of the soil, or if they were given in small amounts, then they can be given under cultivation before sowing. For winter wheat, N₉₀ P₉₀ K₆₀ kg per hectare can be considered as a good norm (including active substances). Fertilizer rate in a specific region should be calculated on the basis of soil and plant diagnostics based on the balance method. As a rule, the annual rate of phosphorus and potassium should be given under the main plow. 20 kg of phosphorus fertilizer should be applied to the rows locally (in a certain area near the row) to increase the winter-hardiness of winter wheat . Each kg of phosphorus given to the row gives an increase of 15-16 kg. Adding micronutrients boron, manganese, zinc, molybdenum and cobalt to the rows along with sprinkling makes it possible to supply the seedlings with qi and elements, and they quickly form a root system and develop well. When feeding with superphosphate in autumn during the bushing phase, the plant's root system and leaves are well formed and they are more resistant to adverse winter conditions. [3, p. 89-92]

Nitrogen fertilizer should be applied in portions. When winter wheat is placed after pure heather, cereal-legumes and perennial leguminous fodder grasses, nitrogen fertilizer is not given in autumn, but it is used in the form of spring feeding. 20% of the annual norm of nitrogen should be given under cultivation when the soil is cultivated before sowing, 50-60% should be given as feeding fertilizer in early spring, and 20-30% should be given in the phase of sprouting-spiking. In addition, in order to increase the amount of protein and gluten in the grain and to obtain strong wheat, nitrogen fertilizer should be given in the form of extra-root feeding at the rate of 30-40 kg of active substance per hectare in the spike-graining phase. Nitrogen is more abundant in winter wheat during the tillering and tillering phase . In crops that are well developed and wintered in favorable conditions, 40-50% of the total rate of nitrogen is given as the first feeding at the end of the bushing and at the beginning of the tuber . During this period, when nitrogen nutrition is normal, bushing is better, the spike develops well, and the number of fertile spikelets in the spike increases. Since the plant mainly needs nitrogen element more in spring, development starts early and the number of productive stems increases. In the first spring feeding, it is necessary to take into account the plant density in the crops. In sparse crops (300 plants per 1 m²), the dose of nitrogen is increased by 10-20 kg per hectare, but in dense crops (more than 400 plants per 1 m²), the dose of nitrogen is reduced by 10-20 kg per hectare. The second feeding is given up to 40-50% of the total norm in the weaning phase [1, p.109-112].

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